

Comparison of the final simulation CON069 with recommended set up for
COMSO5.0_clm6 with observational data

Run CON069 -- 1981-2000

Computing system: blizzard Contact: K.Keuler

Difference CCLM-EOBS (T_{2M})

Run CON069 -- 1981-2000
Computing system: blizzard Contact: K.Keuler
Difference CCLM-EOBS (TMIN_2M)

Run CON069 -- 1981-2000

Computing system: blizzard Contact: K.Keuler

Difference CCLM-EOBS (TMAX_2M)

Run CON069 -- 1981-2000
Computing system: blizzard Contact: K.Keuler
Difference CCLM-EOBS (TOT_PREC)

Run CON069 -- 1981-2000
Computing system: blizzard Contact: K.Keuler
Difference CCLM-EOBS (PMSL)

Run CON069 -- 1981-2000
Computing system: blizzard Contact: K.Keuler
Difference CCLM-CRU (CLCT)

